

The Effect of Rotation and Mutations on Employee Performance Mediated by Job Satisfaction at Class 1 Makassar Determination

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Abstract:- Based on the results of the study, it can be seen that the rotation variable has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Makassar Class I Rutan. So that the hypothesis can be accepted. Mutation variable has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at Class I Rutan Makassar. So that the hypothesis can be accepted. Rotation and mutation variables have a positive and significant simultaneous effect on employee performance at the Makassar Class I Rutan. This proves that the hypothesis can be accepted.

Keywords:- Rotation, Mutations, Employee Performance, Job Satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

As for the mutation phenomenon that occurred in the Class I Rutan Makassar, namely, the employees had to work more extra due to the new job load, adjust to the work environment and create good relationships with superiors and other fellow employees in order to create good cooperation in the future. For employees who have been transferred, they have to move things from the old office to the new office, this takes quite a long time, especially if the transfer is between agencies, causing work on the new position to be delayed.

Organizations should prosper each employee by providing supporting factors in increasing employee job satisfaction with the work they do. Increasing employee job satisfaction will bring progress for the organization to survive in responding to competition that demands government bureaucracy to be reformed and adapted to the dynamics of community demands, therefore efforts to increase employee job satisfaction are a management challenge in dealing with various problems in the scope of employees who support all activities of an organization so that organizational performance is getting better.

II. LITERATUR REVIEW

Based on the background that has been described above, of course, to get human resources who have good performance in government agencies, especially the Class I Rutan Makassar, rotation and mutation are needed and are measured from employee job satisfaction to bring progress to the organization.

According to Mathis and Jackson (2012: 138) "job rotation is the process of moving a person from one job to

another." A technique used to reduce the monotony of an employee's routine. Usually each organization has its own policies in the application of job rotation time. There are periodic (weekly, monthly, yearly) and non-periodic. The advantage of job rotation itself is to develop the capabilities of an employee in doing several different jobs (Mathis and Jackson, 2012: 143).

Basically, employee job satisfaction is an individual thing. Each individual will have a different level of satisfaction according to the value system that applies to him. Robbins and Judge (2012: 108) suggest that employee job satisfaction is a positive feeling about one's work which is the result of an evaluation of its characteristics. Organizations whose employees get job satisfaction tend to be more effective than organizations whose employees get less employee job satisfaction. According to Hasibuan (2016: 114) it is the emotional attitude of someone who enjoys and loves his job. Employee job satisfaction must be created as well as possible so that work morale, dedication, love, and employee discipline increase. Employee job satisfaction is enjoyed on the job, outside of work, and a combination of both.

III. METHODS

Before making a decision, the questionnaires that have been filled out by the respondents are collected, then processed and analyzed so that they can be used for interpretation and as a basis for decision making. In this study, the data analysis used was descriptive analysis to determine the tendency of respondents' responses about their attitudes in answering the research variables. In descriptive analysis, the researcher describes the values of the respondents' responses regarding the research variables.

In this study using the SPSS 24 for Windows program. The data processing is as follows:

1. Scoring (Scoring)

Scoring is an activity in the form of research or expectations in the form of quantitative numbers needed in calculating hypotheses or changing qualitative data into quantitative form. According to Sugiyono (2017), in calculating the scoring a Likert scale is used whose measurements are as follows:

1. Score 5 for the answer strongly agree
2. Score 4 for the answer agree

- 3. Score 3 for the answer quite agree
- 4. Score 2 for the answer disagree
- 5. Score 1 for the answer strongly disagree

RESULT

Table 1. Gender of Respondents.

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	74	59%
Woman	50	41%
Total	124	100%

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2022

Based on the results in the table above, it can be seen that the Makassar Class I Rutan employees who were respondents in this study were 74 men or 59% while for female employees there were 50 people or 41%. So it can be seen that the respondents in this study were mostly male. The underlying reason for this is related to the duties of employees at the Class I Rutan Makassar, where the work of employees is mostly done by men. respondents in this study for the last education of high school were 33 people or 25.4%, then the last education was D3 as many as 30 people or 24.6%, while for employees who 39 people have the latest S1 education or 32% and for employees who have the latest S2 education as many as 22 people or 18%. Based on these data, it can be seen that the majority of respondents in this study have the last education of S1. This shows that in carrying out the duties of the detention house, must have adequate competence so that a lot of S1 education levels are needed which are deemed to have met the requirements.

Table 2. Age of Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage
21-30 Year	36	29.5%
31-40 Year	33	25.4%
41-50 Year	42	34.4%
>50 Year	13	10.7%
Total	124	100%

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2022

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the employees at the Class I Rutan Makassar who became respondents in this study for those aged 50 years were 13 people or 10.7%, for employees aged 41-50 years were 42 people or 34.4%, for employees aged 31-40 years as many as 33 people or 25.4% and those aged 21-30 years as many as 36 people or 29.5%. Thus, it can be seen that the majority of respondents in this study were 41-50 years old. This shows that employees at the Makassar Class I Rutan, aged 41-50 years, are still productive in carrying out tasks, such as services, care and guidance to residents.

Table 3. Respondent's Last Education

Last education	Frequency	percentage
SMA	33	25.4%
D3	30	24.6%
S1	39	32%
S2	22	18%
Total	124	100%

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2022

Based on the results above, it can be seen that the employees at the Makassar Class I Rutan who became

Table 4. Validity Test Results

Variable	Statement Items	Pearson correlation	R Tabel	Information
Employee Rotation (X1)	Statement1	0.380	0,177	Valid
	Statement 2	0.460	0,177	Valid
	Statement3	0.582	0,177	Valid
	Statement4	0.354	0,177	Valid
Mutation Employee(X1)	Statement1	0.380	0,177	Valid
	Statement2	0.460	0,177	Valid
	Statement4	0.582	0,177	Valid
	Statement4	0.354	0,177	Valid
Satisfaction Work (Y)	Statement5	0.515	0,177	Valid
	Statement6	0.399	0,177	Valid
	Statement1	0.559	0,177	Valid
	Statement2	0.373	0,177	Valid
	Statement3	0.416	0,177	Valid
	Statement4	0.195	0,177	Valid
Performance Employee (Z)	Statement5	0.326	0,177	Valid
	Statement1	0.257	0,177	Valid
	Statement2	0.276	0,177	Valid
	Statement3	0.256	0,177	Valid
	Statement4	0.359	0,177	Valid
	Statement5	0.418	0,177	Valid
	Statement6	0.504	0,177	Valid

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2022

Based on the results of the validity test in the table

above, it is known that each statement item has $r_{count} > r_{table}$

(0.177) and is positive. Thus, each of these statements can be declared valid and feasible to continue to conduct research.

Table 5. Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach Alpha	Nilai Alpha	Information
EmployeeRotation (X1)	0,715	0,60	Reliabel
Mutation Employee(X1)	0,610	0,60	Reliabel
Satisfaction Work (Y)	0,612	0,60	Reliabel
Performance Employee (Z)	0,607	0,60	Reliabel

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2022

Based on the results of the reliability test in the table above, it shows that each variable has a Cronbach alpha > 0.60. Thus, the Employee Rotation Variable (X1), Employee Transfer (X2) Job satisfaction (Y) and employee performance (Z) can be declared reliable.

Fig 1. Heteroscedasticity Test

Source: Data processed by researchers, 2022

IV. DISCUSSION

Based on the discussion of the previous chapter, which in this study aims to determine the effect of leadership style, work motivation and work environment on employee performance at Rutan Class I Makassar. From the research results that have been obtained, it can be concluded as follows: Rotation variable has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at Class I Rutan Makassar.

So that the hypothesis can be accepted. Mutation variable has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at Class I Rutan Makassar. So that the hypothesis can be accepted. Rotation and mutation variables have a positive and significant simultaneous effect on employee performance at the Makassar Class I Rutan. This proves that the hypothesis can be accepted

V. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

Based on the discussion of the previous chapter, which in this study aims to determine the effect of leadership style, work motivation and work environment on employee performance at Rutan Class I Makassar. From the research results that have been obtained, it can be concluded as follows:

1. Rotation variable has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at Class I Rutan Makassar. So that the hypothesis can be accepted.
2. Mutation variable has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance at Class I Rutan Makassar. So that the hypothesis can be accepted.
3. Variables of rotation and mutation have a positive and significant effect simultaneously on employee performance at the Makassar Class I Rutan. This proves that the hypothesis can be accepted

Based on the conclusions that have been described previously, the suggestions that researchers can give are as follows:

1. For Class I Makassar Rutan, to be able to maintain good employee performance, and always communicate everything related to the work environment in achieving tasks with clear information, and with leaders paying attention to what subordinates want, will motivate employees to work what the Organization expects
2. Every employee should take advantage of every opportunity to be able to carry out his work tasks to be more meaningful and responsible according to the characteristics of the job in order to increase job satisfaction. This can be achieved by holding regular meetings to discuss job characteristics to make it

Based on the results of the normality test using the Komogorov-Smirnov statistical test in the table above, with N= 124 it can be seen that Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) shows a value of 0.163 which means it is greater than 0.05, so it can be concluded that the residual data is normally distributed more meaningful with other employees.

For further research with similar topics, it is recommended to add other variables such as organizational culture, discipline, work competence, and others that can affect employee performance and use other analytical methods and it is recommended to expand the scope of research so that the research results obtained have a wider impact. and get better benefits in the future.

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